

1 **Legends for Extended Data Figures 1 to 10** (Zangari, Stehling et al.)

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4 **Extended Data Fig. 1. D-Cys impairs proliferation of a number of different cancer cell**
5 **types grown under 2D or 3D conditions. a,** Colony formation assay of A549 cells in the
6 absence (w/o) or presence of either the L- or D-enantiomer of each proteinogenic amino acid.
7 Each L- or D-amino acid was added to standard medium at similar concentrations as those
8 already present in the medium. D-Cys was used at 100 μ M **b,** Colony formation assay for
9 various cell types, including BZR, LuCa62, Calu1, JL1, ZL34, and A375 cells cultured in the
10 absence (w/o) or presence of 100 μ M D-Cys. **c,d,** Growth of A549 (**c**) and LuCa62 (**d**)
11 spheroids in the absence (w/o) or presence of indicated D-Cys concentrations. All data are
12 presented as mean \pm SD of n=3 biological replicates. Spheroid volumes at the indicated days
13 of treatment were compared by 2-way ANOVA and Dunnett's multiple comparisons test; **e,**
14 Colony formation assays for HCT-116, DLD-1, HeLa and H2052/484 tumour cells in the
15 absence (w/o) or presence of D-Cys. **f,** Determination of IC50 values using nonlinear fit,
16 inhibitor conc vs response, for D-cystine or D-Cys for growth of A549 (left) or MDA-MB-231
17 cells (right).

18 **Extended Data Fig. 2. Genome-wide CRISPR/Cas9 knockout screening identifies genes**
19 **increasing the D-Cys toxicity in A549 cells. a,** Volcano plot showing the most significant
20 proteins whose depletion boosts D-Cys toxicity. Among the top hits are several glycolytic
21 genes and the mitochondrial ISC protein glutaredoxin 5 (GLRX5); SLC3A12 and SLC7A11
22 (red bars) are mentioned for comparison. Q values were calculated using MAGeCK, which
23 includes a correction for multiple comparisons. See also Supplementary Table 2 for detailed
24 results. **b, c,** Validation of CRISPR/Cas9 KO of *SLC3A2* (CD98), *SLC7A11* (xCT), or *NFE2L2*
25 (*NRF2*) genes in A549 cells by immunoblotting of corresponding proteins (molecular masses
26 in parentheses). Representative blots of n=3 (**b**) and 2 (**c**) biological replicates. **d,** A549 cells
27 were cultured in full culture medium in the absence (---) or presence of the reductant TCEP
28 (375 μ M), in the absence (Ctrl) or presence of the xCT inhibitor erastin (1 μ M). Samples either
29 did not receive additional Cys supplementation (w/o), or were supplemented with 500 μ M L-
30 Cys or D-Cys for a total of three days as indicated. Cells were harvested and total protein yield
31 was determined (mean \pm SD). The efficiency of erastin treatment was analyzed by 2-way
32 repeated measures ANOVA and Bonferroni posttest; symbols indicate matching samples of
33 n=3 biological replicates. **e,** Wild-type or knock-out (KO) A549 cells were cultured for three
34 days in full culture medium in the presence of erastin (Era) and/or 500 μ M D-Cys as indicated.
35 Intracellular L-Cys and D-Cys levels were determined as a measure of cellular Cys import.
36 Results are mean \pm SD of n=3 biological replicates for cells cultured in the presence (D-Cys)
37 or absence (w/o) of D-cys; n=2 biological replicates (consisting of 3 technical replicates each)
38 for the other conditions. Unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-tests were used for comparison
39 between cells cultured with and without (w/o) D-Cys. **f,** BEAS-2B cells were cultured for three
40 days in full culture medium in the absence or presence of 500 μ M D-Cys as indicated, and the
41 cellular L- and D-Cys content was determined in n=2 experimental series as a measure of Cys
42 import.

43 **Extended Data Fig. 3. xCT (*SLC7A11*) and CD98 (*SLC3A2*) expression is associated with**
44 **D-Cys sensitivity. a,b**, Immunoblotting of xCT and CD98 in various cell types that display
45 sensitivity (**a**) or resistance (**b**) to D-Cys. **c**, Doxycycline-induced (co-)expression of C-
46 terminally FLAG-tagged xCT and CD98 was analysed by anti-FLAG immunoblotting in
47 BEAS-2B cells stably transduced by lentiviral infection. **d**, HeLa cells were transiently
48 transfected to co-express C-terminally FLAG-tagged xCT and CD98, or the reference protein
49 EGFP as indicated, cultured in absence (w/o) or presence of D-Cys for three days, and analysed
50 by anti-FLAG immunoblotting. **e**, Protein yield of HeLa cell cultures from (**d**). Data are
51 presented as mean \pm SD; * $P < 0.05$; ns, not significant. Comparison by 2-way repeated
52 measures ANOVA and Bonferroni posttest; symbols indicate matching samples of n=4
53 biological replicates (one series lacks xCT/CD98 values). Representative blots of n=4 (**a-b**),
54 n=1 for (**c**) and n= 4 (**d**) biological replicates are shown. β -actin and α -tubulin (TUBA) were
55 used as loading controls (molecular masses in parentheses).

56 **Extended Data Fig. 4. Proteomic analysis of A549 cells cultured in the presence or absence**
57 **of D-Cys or L-Cys.** A549 cells were cultured for three days in DMEM containing 200 μ M L-
58 cystine (w/o) or in the same medium supplemented with either 500 μ M D-Cys or L-Cys, and a
59 proteomic analysis was performed. **a**, Volcano plot showing proteins that vary among the
60 different conditions. Different comparisons have been made according to the protein colour
61 code shown in the box. **b**, List of the most downregulated mitochondrial proteins in D-Cys-
62 treated cells (orange dots from **a**). See also Suppl. Table S2 for a more detailed list of proteins
63 analysed and their comparison among the different culture conditions. **c**, Immunoblot analyses
64 of representative OXPHOS protein subunit levels in indicated cell lines cultured in the absence
65 (w/o) or presence (+) of D-Cys. VDAC1 served as loading control. Representative blots of n=4
66 (for A549 cells) and n=2 (for MDA-MA-231 and BEAS-2B cell) biological replicates are
67 shown.

68 **Extended Data Fig. 5. D-Cys decreases oxygen consumption rates and triggers ROS and**
69 **lipid peroxidation in A549 cells. a,b,** Basal and maximal oxygen consumption rates (OCR)
70 of BEAS-2B (**a**) or A549 cells (**b**) cultured in the absence (w/o) or presence of 500 μ M D-Cys
71 for three days. Data of n=3 (**a**) and n=4 (**b**) biological replicates are presented as mean \pm SD
72 and were analysed by 2-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparisons test. **c-d,**
73 Quantitation of FACS-analyses of ROS production in A549 cells cultured in the absence (w/o)
74 or presence of 500 μ M D-Cys for three days, using either MitoSOX (determination of
75 mitochondrial ROS in n=3 biological replicates) (**c**) or BD C11 (determination of lipid
76 peroxidation in n=6 biological replicates) (**d**). Mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) \pm SD is
77 shown; data were analysed by unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test. **e,** A549 cells have been
78 cultured under normoxia (21% oxygen, O₂) or hypoxia (1% oxygen, O₂) for 72 h, either in the
79 absence (w/o) or presence of 500 mM D-Cys. Cells were then counted (upper panel) or stained
80 with cresyl violet (lower panel). Cell counts of n=3 biological replicates are presented as mean
81 \pm SD and were analysed by unpaired two-tailed Student's *t*-test. **f,** Lack of effect of ferrostatin1
82 (Fer-1) on D-Cys-induced toxicity. A549 cells were cultured for 72 h with or without D-Cys
83 and with the indicated concentrations of Fer-1 added freshly from day 1 to day 3. Following
84 the 72 h culture period cells of n=3 biological replicates were counted, and the results are
85 presented as mean \pm SD. The comparison was performed by an unpaired two-tailed Student's
86 *t*-test.
87

88 **Extended Data Fig. 6. D-Cys induces Fe-S protein defects in xCT-CD98-overproducing**
89 **HeLa cells.** HeLa cells were transiently transfected to co-express C-terminally FLAG-tagged
90 CD98 and xCT, or the reference protein EGFP as indicated. Cells were cultured in the absence
91 (w/o) or presence of 500 μ M D-Cys for three days (cf. Extended Data Fig. 3d,e). **a-b**, Cell
92 extracts were analysed by immunoblotting of the indicated mitochondrial proteins or the lipoyl
93 cofactor. ATP5F1A/B and VDAC1 served as loading controls. **c-f**, Mitochondria-containing
94 organellar fractions, obtained by digitonin-based cell separation, were analysed for the specific
95 enzyme activities of mitochondrial aconitase (mtAco), succinate dehydrogenase (SDH,
96 respiratory complex II), citrate synthase (CS), and cytochrome *c* oxidase (COX, respiratory
97 complex IV). **g**, Cell samples were analysed by immunoblotting of the indicated cytosolic-
98 nuclear proteins. α -tubulin (TUBA) served as loading control. **h-i**, Cytosolic fractions obtained
99 by digitonin-based cell separation were analysed for the specific enzyme activities of cytosolic
100 aconitase (cytAco) and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH). Representative blots of n=4 biological
101 replicates are shown. Numbers in parentheses indicate observed molecular masses. C-I to C-
102 V, OXPHOS complexes I to V. Data are presented as mean \pm SD; * P < 0.05; ** P < 0.01; *** P
103 < 0.001; ns, not significant. Symbols indicate matching samples of n=4 biological replicates.
104

105 **Extended Data Fig. 7. NFS1 can generate a D-Cys-ketimine intermediate but is unable to**
106 **mobilise sulfur. a,** Cartoon of the reaction cycle of the cysteine desulfurase NFS1 with L-Cys.
107 The resting state of the enzyme comprises an internal (i.e. enzyme-bound) aldimine, by which
108 the pyridoxal phosphate (PLP) cofactor is covalently bound to Lys258 as a Schiff base (1).
109 Cys381 and His156 are positioned close to the PLP. Binding of free L-Cys creates an external
110 (i.e. non-enzyme-bound) L-Cys-aldimine (2) which tautomerizes (catalysed by His156) to an
111 external L-Cys-ketimine (3). The sulfur atom (yellow ball) can be released from L-Cys-
112 ketimine and transferred to Cys381, thereby creating an external L-Ala-ketimine and a
113 persulfide (-SSH) on Cys381 (4). The resting state 1 of the enzyme with its internal aldimine
114 is regenerated by rapid release of free L-Ala. Residue numbering is for human NFS1. The
115 reaction scheme was adopted from Refs. 41,42. **b,c,** Time courses of the generation of the L-
116 and D-Cys-ketimine intermediate (absorption at 340 nm, blue) from the internal aldimine (416
117 nm, red) by the indicated (NIA)₂ complexes. Data were taken from the spectra shown in Fig.
118 4b,c. **d,** Cartoon of the NFS1 reaction with D-Cys. The enzyme can efficiently and rapidly form
119 the D-Cys-aldimine (2) and -ketimine intermediates (3), but for steric reasons cannot transfer
120 the sulfur to Cys381, unlike with L-Cys (**a**). For 3D inspection of the models in parts **a,d**, a
121 Chimera X session has been added as Supplementary File 1 (L_D-Cys_Cycle_final.X.py),
122 using the following 3D structures: PDB ID: 7E6D, 6O13, 6O11, 7XEJ.

123 **Extended Data Fig. 8. Electron density maps around pyridoxal-phosphate (PLP) in the**
124 **L-propargylglycine (PG)-containing (NIAU)₂ crystal structure.** The 2Fo-DFc (blue;
125 contoured at 0.5 sigma) and Fo-DFc (orange; 2.5 sigma) difference maps were calculated after
126 5 refinement macrocycles in Phenix of the model from which the PG-PLP, the sidechain of
127 Lys258, and residues 377-387 were excluded (PDB ID: 8TVT). While the density for the loop
128 is weak, it was possible to build backbones of residues Gly378-Cys381 and Ala384-Glu387.
129 Most of the sidechains in this region were not visible and were not modeled. The Fo-DFc map
130 clearly shows that Lys258 is not covalently bound to PLP, thus defining PG-PLP as an external
131 aldimine. There appears to be density at low level to allow placing the sidechain of Cys381 in
132 one possible conformation, where it points toward the PG sidechain.
133

134 **Extended Data Fig. 9. D-Cys induces Fe-S protein defects particularly at low cell**
135 **densities. a**, A549 cells were seeded at low density (LD, 5×10^3 cells/cm²) or high density (HD,
136 60×10^3 cells/cm²), cultured in the absence (w/o) or presence of 500 μ M D-Cys for LD cultures
137 and 1 mM for HD cultures. After three days cells were harvested and counted; experiments
138 were done in technical triplicates and performed twice; 2-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's
139 multiple comparisons test; **** $P < 0.0001$. **b-c**, Indicated numbers of A549 cells were seeded
140 into 25 cm² flasks, cultured in the absence (w/o) or presence of 500 μ M D-Cys for a total of
141 three days and harvested. Protein yield of each culture at harvest (**b**), and relative protein yield
142 of D-Cys-treated cultures in comparison to untreated cultures (**c**) are presented. **d**, A549 cells
143 were cultured at LD or HD conditions as indicated in (**a**). After 15 h, the cellular D-Cys content
144 was measured by the D-Cys luciferase assay, and expressed relative to the HD value. **e**, Protein
145 levels of xCT and CD98 in cells from (**b**) were determined by immunoblotting. α -tubulin
146 (TUBA) served as loading control. **f**, Immunofluorescence confocal analysis of xCT and
147 phalloidin in A549 cells cultured at LD (top) to HD (bottom) conditions (left panels). Note the
148 colocalization of xCT and phalloidin at HD. Z sections taken at the horizontal middle position
149 of the respective XY view (left) are shown in right panels. Images are representative of $n=2$
150 biological replicates. **g,h**, Cell samples from (**b**) were analysed by immunoblotting against the
151 indicated mitochondrial proteins or lipoyl cofactor. VDAC1 served as loading control. C-I to
152 C-V, OXPHOS complexes I to V. **i,j**, Total cell lysates of cells from (**c**) were analysed for the
153 specific enzyme activities of total cellular aconitase (ACO) and succinate dehydrogenase
154 (SDH, respiratory complex II). **k**, Cell samples were analysed by immunoblotting against the
155 indicated cytosolic-nuclear CIA and Fe-S proteins. TUBA served as loading control. **l**, Crude
156 membrane preparations of cells from (**b**) were analysed for the specific enzyme activity of
157 cytochrome *c* oxidase (COX, respiratory complex IV). Representative blots and images are
158 shown (**e-h,k**). Numbers in parentheses indicate observed molecular masses. Data obtained
159 from $n=3$ biological replicates are presented as mean \pm SD, with individual symbols indicating
160 matching samples (**b-d,i,j,l**); Comparisons were performed by 2-way repeated measures
161 ANOVA and Bonferroni posttests (**b,c,i,j,l**); * $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$;
162 **** $P < 0.0001$; ns, not significant.

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164 **Extended Data Fig. 10. D-Cys clearance by D-amino acid oxidase and its lack of adverse**
165 **effects. a.** Immunodeficient mice were administered 200 μ L of D-Cys (15 mg/mL in PBS)
166 intraperitoneally, vehicle only (Veh), or the D-amino acid oxidase (DAAO) inhibitor 6-
167 hydroxy-2-(naphthalen-1-ylmethyl)-1,2,4-triazine-3,5(2H,4H)-dione (Ref. 69) (DAAO inh, 30
168 mg/kg, orally). A fourth group received both D-Cys and the DAAO inhibitor. Blood samples
169 were collected from the tail at 1 and 2 h post-administration for the analysis of L-cystine and
170 D-cystine levels via chiral chromatography (n=2 each). **b-e.** Immunodeficient mice were fed a
171 chow diet supplemented with either L-cystine or D-cystine for 35 days. Additionally, daily
172 intraperitoneal (IP) and subcutaneous (SC) injections of D-cystine or vehicle were administered
173 as detailed in Methods. Body weight was monitored throughout the experimental protocol (**b**).
174 Three weeks after starting the diet, mice were euthanized, and samples were collected for the
175 measurement of creatinine (**c**), alanine aminotransferase (ALAT; **d**), and aspartate
176 aminotransferase (ASAT; **e**). Data obtained from individual animals are presented as mean \pm
177 SD for control and D-Cys-treated groups (n=10 each). Statistical analyses were performed
178 using unpaired, two-tailed Student's *t*-tests.
179